

Unified Signal Quality and Geometry-Aware Satellite Weighting via Deep Learning for Smartphone GNSS Positioning

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Abstract—Existing GNSS positioning methods typically optimize signal quality and satellite geometry separately, limiting their potential for accuracy improvement. In this paper, we propose an integrated framework that leverages both aspects jointly to enhance positioning accuracy. Our approach follows a three-stage pipeline: first, raw GNSS measurements are processed into features that capture both signal quality and geometric indicators; second, a machine learning model evaluates each satellite’s contribution to positioning accuracy using these combined features; third, the predicted scores are used as adaptive weights in a Weighted Least Squares (WLS) estimator to compute the final position. A key feature is our geometry-derived inputs that capture essential Dilution of Precision information without expensive matrix operations like ASMD (Angular Spread to Mean Direction). We trained and evaluated multiple regression models using approximately 1.5 million samples generated from the Google Smartphone Decimeter Challenge dataset. A Multilayer Perceptron architecture delivered the best performance, achieving a Mean Absolute Error of 0.204. Our ML-enhanced Weighted Least Squares (ML-WLS) approach reduced mean positioning error by 39.2% compared to conventional WLS, with improvements ranging from 33.2% to 72.2% across different error percentiles. We validated the approach across multiple smartphone models, observing consistent performance gains and standard deviation reductions up to 78%, demonstrating that the approach is efficient for large-scale use.

Index Terms—GNSS, smartphone positioning, weighted least squares, satellite weighting, machine learning, satellite scoring, urban canyon, multipath, NLOS.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid development of autonomous driving, robotics, precision agriculture and Industry 4.0, accurate positioning has become increasingly critical [1]. Many applications now require sub-meter or even centimeter-level accuracy to work properly. For example, lane-level autonomous vehicles need positioning accuracy better than 1 meter [2], precision agriculture may need below 10 cm [3], and automated port operation requires less than 50 cm for safe handling of vehicles and containers. These requirements exceed the limitations of traditional GNSS positioning solutions and motivate the search for better methods.

Global Navigation Satellite Systems, such as GPS, GLONASS, Galileo and BeiDou, are the most widely used technology for positioning. Under open-sky conditions, a single-frequency GNSS receiver can usually achieve 1–5 meter

TABLE I
ANALYSIS OF GNSS ERROR SOURCES AND THEIR MAGNITUDES

Error Source	Open-Sky	Urban
Satellite Clock Error	~0.5–1 m	~0.5–1 m
Ephemeris Error	~1–2 m	~1–2 m
Ionospheric Delay	~1–5 m	~1–5 m
Tropospheric Delay	~0.5–2 m	~0.5–2 m
Multipath	<1 m	5–50 m
NLOS	Rare	10–100+ m
Satellite Geometry (DOP)	1–2 m	5–20 m

accuracy [4]. Although this performance is sufficient for general navigation, it is not adequate for many safety-critical and industrial applications. More advanced techniques like RTK or PPP can provide centimeter-level precision, but they require correction data or infrastructure which is not available everywhere [5]. Therefore, enhancing the performance of low-cost single-receiver GNSS remains an important research goal.

Urban and industrial environments affect GNSS performance. Tall buildings block satellite signals, reflective surfaces cause multipath, and non-line-of-sight (NLOS) reception degrades pseudorange measurements. Under such conditions, positioning error frequently exceeds 10–50 meters, and in dense urban canyons it may even surpass 100 meters [6]. Another major factor is satellite geometry, which is often quantified by Dilution of Precision (DOP). When visible satellites are not well distributed, DOP values become high, amplifying the error and reducing positioning accuracy [7], [8].

To address these problems, many methods have been proposed in the literature. Satellite selection methods choose only satellites that meet certain thresholds such as elevation angle or signal strength [9]. Scoring methods assign weights to satellites based on indicators such as elevation, signal strength, carrier-to-noise ratio (C/N_0), or pseudorange residuals [10]. Geometry optimization methods try to find satellite subsets that improve DOP or modified DOP metrics. However, satellite selection may discard useful signals, scoring methods depend heavily on the chosen metric, and geometry optimization can become computationally expensive when explicit DOP calculation or matrix inversion is needed [11].

Recent works have shown promising advances. For example, some authors compared multiple optimization algorithms (ABC, ACO, GA, PSO, and SA) to select a subset of satellites based on the weighted GDOP minimization, demonstrating that the satellite geometry and signal quality can be jointly

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Fig. 1. General workflow of the proposed approach.

considered [12]. In urban areas, machine learning has also been used to increase the GPS positioning accuracy by decreasing the weights of the multipath-affected measurements, reporting improvements in the range of 18–30

In this paper, we propose a data-driven approach organized into three stages (Fig. 1). First, raw GNSS measurements are processed and transformed into meaningful features that combine signal quality and geometric indicators. Second, a machine learning workflow is applied to train and select the best-performing model that scores each satellite based on its expected contribution to positioning accuracy. Third, the predicted scores are used as adaptive weights in a Weighted Least Squares (WLS) estimator to compute the final position. This structured pipeline aims to improve positioning accuracy in challenging environments while maintaining computational efficiency.

A. Proposed Contributions

- **Integration of signal quality and geometric factors:** We propose a data-driven satellite contribution score that quantifies each satellite’s impact on position estimation by combining both signal quality and geometric configuration in a unified framework.
- **Novel geometry-derived features:** We introduce novel features derived from DOP geometry that capture essential positioning information without requiring explicit matrix inversion or evaluating thousands of DOP values for different satellite subsets. This significantly reduces computational burden while preserving geometric insight.
- **Machine learning framework for satellite scoring:** We develop a machine learning model that combines signal quality indicators (C/N_0 , elevation, signal strength) and geometric indicators (derived from satellite visibility and geometry) to compute a robust score for each satellite (Fig. 2).
- **Integration with WLS:** We integrate these scores as adaptive weights in a Weighted Least Squares position estimator, improving robustness and accuracy of single-receiver GNSS positioning, especially in urban or partially obstructed environments.

Fig. 2. Illustration of ML-based satellite scoring.

We train and evaluate multiple regression models using approximately 1.5 million samples from the Google Smartphone Decimeter Challenge (GSDC) dataset, which contains raw GNSS smartphone measurements together with high-accuracy ground truth collected from commercial smartphones across urban and highway routes. Under challenging conditions including multipath, NLOS, and urban geometry, we validate our method and demonstrate that it significantly reduces positioning error compared to conventional approaches.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Machine Learning for Satellite Selection and Classification

Machine learning techniques have been widely explored to identify and exclude poor-quality GNSS measurements in challenging environments. The main focus is developing classification algorithms that can accurately distinguish each satellite signal as either useful (line-of-sight, LOS) or unreliable (non-line-of-sight, NLOS or multipath-affected) using data-driven models.

Recent work has explored machine-learning-based quality assessment of GNSS observations by fusing multiple indicators rather than relying on a single metric. For example, Li et al. [16] propose a comprehensive observation-quality classification framework that combines unsupervised k -means clustering with supervised KNN to automatically label and classify GNSS data quality using four core features: data integrity rate, C/N_0 (CNR), pseudorange multipath, and the number of observations per slip (cycle-slip related). They report strong correlations among multipath, C/N_0 , and observations-per-slip and achieve over 90% average classification correctness via cross-validation, highlighting the value of multi-indicator fusion for objective GNSS data-quality evaluation.

Li et al. [17] found that a random forest classifier using features including C/N_0 , satellite elevation angle, and pseudorange residuals could distinguish NLOS signals with approximately 93.4% accuracy, providing a foundation for discarding or down-weighting unreliable satellites. Ozeki and Kubo [18] demonstrated that using a Support Vector Machine (SVM)

classifier with RINEX-derived features to detect NLOS signals, combined with pseudorange residual consistency checks, eliminated erroneous measurements and improved the fraction of sub-10 meter horizontal positioning errors by over 80% in dense urban trials.

These learning-based classifiers have the practical benefit that they do not require detailed 3D building models or extensive infrastructure support, which is a significant benefit for real-time urban navigation applications where detailed environmental models may not be available.

Beyond binary classification approaches, researchers have developed machine-learning techniques that cast signal quality assessment and error mitigation as regression problems. Lee et al. [19] proposed a support vector regression (SVR) model that maps each satellite's elevation and azimuth to an expected multipath error magnitude, effectively constructing a site-specific multipath bias map. When applied in a dense downtown urban environment, the resulting bias compensation achieved 58.4% horizontal and 77.7% vertical error reductions.

Machine learning techniques can also be leveraged for conservative satellite subset selection in urban positioning. Kim and Seo [15] propose an ensemble-based strategy in which three independently trained classifiers (random forest, gradient boosting decision tree, and SVM) perform LOS/NLOS classification, and a satellite is used for positioning only when all models unanimously agree on its label and their confidence exceeds a threshold. In experiments with real urban canyon GPS data, the unanimous voting strategy improved the ZSM (Zonotope Shadow Matching) positioning success rate to 99.3%.

B. Satellite Scoring in Weighted Least Squares Frameworks

To mitigate measurement errors rather than completely discarding potentially useful satellites, numerous research works have focused on developing methods to adjust weights in the position solution based on per-satellite signal quality indicators or learned scoring functions. In the standard Weighted Least Squares (WLS) algorithm, each observation is weighted by the inverse of its expected measurement variance.

Traditionally, these weights have been determined from relatively simple mathematical models using the satellite's elevation angle or carrier-to-noise ratio as a direct proxy for measurement noise characteristics [20]. Classical weighting schemes include the SIGMA- ϵ model (variance derived from SNR measurements) and SIGMA- Δ (using SNR-elevation template), as well as various empirical exponential models based on SNR values. However, in challenging urban environments, the SNR can fluctuate unpredictably due to complex signal reflections, and fixed SNR/elevation-based weighting schemes often fail to accurately capture true measurement quality [21].

Researchers have created adaptive weighting models to overcome these constraints. The HK model was presented by Park et al. [22], which classifies signals according to the standard deviation of their SNR over time and assigns weights appropriately. They found that the SNR variance of NLOS-affected signals is significantly higher than that of direct LOS

signals. Their strategy produced significant accuracy benefits by down-weighting samples with unstable SNR behavior; in deep urban canyons, the horizontal RMSE decreased from 13.0 m to 4.7 m, indicating a nearly 65% reduction in positioning errors.

Using statistical classifiers or machine learning to determine the best weighting schemes is another significant advancement. An early example was shown by Lyu and Gao [23], who developed a weight system that significantly devalues NLOS-classified signals after training an SVM classifier to differentiate between LOS and NLOS readings. Their SVM-based weighting beat traditional C/N_0 models by 65.4% horizontally and 85.0% vertically when integrated into a single-frequency precise point positioning (SFPPP) system.

More recently, Li et al. [17] presented a hybrid weighting approach that uses the predicted NLOS probability of the random forest classifier as a consideration in weight computation, combining machine learning outputs with classical measures. They achieved remarkable accuracy gains in dense urban environments using this probability-weighted WLS approach—ML-based signal exclusion alone improved horizontal positioning by about 69%, and applying novel weighting improved it by 40% compared to the unweighted solution.

C. DOP-Based Approaches to Enhance Geometry

Optimizing satellite geometry using Dilution of Precision (DOP) metrics is another significant area of research. DOP quantifies how range errors are amplified into position errors by satellite-receiver geometry; lower DOP values correspond to more advantageous geometric configurations. In actuality, one can choose the ideal subset that minimizes DOP measures like PDOP or GDOP when there are more satellites accessible than are necessary.

However, brute-force checking of all possible satellite subsets for the lowest GDOP becomes computationally intractable with large multi-constellation scenarios. For example, choosing 12 satellites out of 24 available requires over 2.7 million DOP evaluations [24]. Msaewe et al. [25] even observed cases where adding satellites did not improve accuracy despite lowering GDOP, due to unmodeled errors.

To improve geometry without doing an exhaustive search, researchers have used both analytical and heuristic methods. A "maximum volume" approach that chooses satellites that form the largest geometric structure was first presented by Kihara and Okada [26]. A quasi-optimal selection approach for real-time use was presented by Park and How [27], and it was later extended into a recursive scheme [28] by Liu et al.

Modern DOP-based methods often combine geometry and signal quality through Weighted DOP (WGDOP) approaches, which incorporate measurement quality into DOP calculation. Chen et al. formalized WGDOP for efficient satellite selection and provided low-computation formulations that avoid heavy matrix inversion [29]. More recently, Zuo et al. proposed a WGDOP-based selection criterion in which near-real-time observation accuracy is estimated within a sliding window, reporting consistent improvements over GDOP-only selection [30].

To find subsets minimizing WGDOP efficiently, researchers have applied various optimization algorithms. Alluhaybi et al. [12] implemented five metaheuristic algorithms for optimal subset selection (ABC, ACO, GA, PSO, and SA) and found that the Artificial Bee Colony algorithm was most practical, reliably identifying the optimal subset even when choosing 15 satellites out of 31 available (over 300 million possible combinations).

Other innovative methods include learning-based approaches. Singh et al. designed an end-to-end deep neural network to select optimal satellite subsets aiming to minimize GDOP [31]. Jing et al. combined hierarchical clustering with subset refinement, achieving sub-4 millisecond selection times while matching optimal GDOP performance [11].

D. Hybrid Methods and Integrated Approaches

In complex urban environments, no single technique may be sufficient. Hybrid approaches have emerged that combine signal-based filtering, geometry optimization, and sometimes external sensors or environmental models. Ng et al. [32] demonstrated that combining machine learning LOS/NLOS classifiers with 3D city model shadow matching significantly improved urban position fixes. Ozeki et al. [18] combined SVM-based NLOS detection with traditional pseudorange residual consistency checks, yielding over 80% improvement in horizontal accuracy. Hsu et al. proposed a hybrid method fusing 3D building models with RAIM-like satellite exclusion, cutting incidence of large positioning errors by approximately 36% in deep urban canyons [33].

III. PROPOSED APPROACH

In conventional WLS-based GNSS positioning, the weight matrix \mathbf{W} is typically modeled as a function of signal/measurement-quality indicators, i.e., $\mathbf{W} = w(\text{signal features})$, where weights are commonly set proportional to the inverse of the observation variance:

$$\mathbf{W} = \text{diag}(\sigma_1^{-2}, \dots, \sigma_m^{-2}). \quad (1)$$

In this work, we extend this by making the weighting function depend on both signal quality and constellation geometry:

$$\mathbf{W} = w(\text{signal features}, \text{geometric features}). \quad (2)$$

Specifically, we introduce geometry-derived descriptors such as Angular Spread to Mean Direction (ASMD) to capture how each satellite contributes to the overall spatial distribution. We then train a machine-learning model on an open, robust dataset to predict a per-satellite score from the combined signal and geometric features. Finally, these predicted scores are injected as the diagonal elements of \mathbf{W} in the WLS solver, yielding an ML-aided WLS estimation that adapts satellite weighting to both measurement reliability and geometric contribution, as illustrated in Fig. 3.

A. Feature Engineering

From the raw measurements dataset, we extract and engineer features grouped into *signal quality indicators* and *geometric indicators*.

1) *Signal Quality Indicators: Carrier-to-noise density ratio (C/N_0)*: Indicates signal strength per unit bandwidth, expressed in dB-Hz as:

$$C/N_0 = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{C}{N_0} \right) \quad (3)$$

where C is carrier power and N_0 is noise spectral density. Higher C/N_0 values generally correspond to more reliable measurements [34].

Elevation angle (θ): The angle between the satellite and the local horizon. Satellites at low elevation are more prone to multipath and atmospheric effects [9].

Azimuth angle (ϕ): The satellite's direction in the horizontal plane, measured clockwise from north. This feature helps capture the spatial distribution of satellites.

Pseudorange uncertainty (σ_ρ): Reported by the receiver, it reflects the estimated error standard deviation of the pseudorange measurement.

Accumulated Delta Range (ADR) uncertainty ($\sigma_{\Delta\rho}$): Represents the uncertainty of the accumulated carrier-phase measurement (ADR), often affected by cycle slips and signal interruptions [35].

2) *Geometric Indicators: Angular Spread to Mean Direction (ASMD)*: We compute the unit vector from the receiver to each satellite \mathbf{s}_i , and the mean direction vector across all visible satellites $\bar{\mathbf{s}}$. The angular separation is given by:

$$\theta_{\text{mean},i} = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\mathbf{s}_i \cdot \bar{\mathbf{s}}}{\|\mathbf{s}_i\| \|\bar{\mathbf{s}}\|} \right) \quad (4)$$

We then use $\sin(\theta_{\text{mean},i})$ and $\cos(\theta_{\text{mean},i})$ as features to capture how evenly satellites are distributed.

Geometry matrix features: The geometry matrix \mathbf{G} is defined as [36]:

$$\mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{x_1 - x_r}{\rho_1} & \frac{y_1 - y_r}{\rho_1} & \frac{z_1 - z_r}{\rho_1} & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{x_n - x_r}{\rho_n} & \frac{y_n - y_r}{\rho_n} & \frac{z_n - z_r}{\rho_n} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where (x_i, y_i, z_i) is the position of satellite s_i , (x_r, y_r, z_r) is the receiver position, and ρ_i is the geometric range. From \mathbf{G} , we compute:

- Determinant: $\det(\mathbf{G}^\top \mathbf{G})$, reflecting overall satellite spread.
- Trace: $\text{tr}(\mathbf{G}^\top \mathbf{G})$, reflecting the cumulative projection strength.

3) *Target Variable (Satellite Score)*: For each satellite j , we compute the positioning error using all satellites (base_error) and then with satellite j removed (sub_error $_j$). The satellite score is defined as:

$$\text{sat_score}_j = \frac{\text{sub_error}_j}{\text{base_error}} = \frac{\|\mathbf{p}_{\text{true}} - \mathbf{p}_{(-j)}\|}{\|\mathbf{p}_{\text{true}} - \mathbf{p}_{\text{base}}\|} \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{p}_{true} is the high-accuracy ground-truth position, \mathbf{p}_{base} is the position estimated using all satellites, and $\mathbf{p}_{(-j)}$ is the position estimated excluding satellite j .

A $\text{sat_score} > 1$ indicates the satellite improves accuracy, while $\text{sat_score} < 1$ indicates it degrades accuracy. After preprocessing, the dataset is used to train regression models to predict the satellite score from the engineered features.

B. Machine Learning Workflow

We evaluate several regression models to map features to satellite scores:

- Linear Regression (LR),
- Random Forest (RF) [37],
- Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP),
- Support Vector Regression (SVR) [38],
- Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) [39].

The trained model outputs a predicted score for each satellite, which serves as the weight input to WLS.

C. WLS Integration with Learned Scores

The GNSS position solution is formulated as a nonlinear least-squares problem:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}} \left\| \mathbf{W}^{1/2} (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x})) \right\|^2 \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{x} = [x_r, y_r, z_r, b]^\top$ is the unknown receiver position and clock bias, \mathbf{y} is the vector of pseudorange observations, $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x})$ is the vector of modeled ranges, and $\mathbf{W} = \text{diag}(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)$ is the weighting matrix.

The WLS update step is given by:

$$\Delta \mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{H}^\top \mathbf{W} \mathbf{H})^{-1} \mathbf{H}^\top \mathbf{W} \Delta \boldsymbol{\rho} \quad (8)$$

where $\Delta \boldsymbol{\rho}$ is the pseudorange residual vector and \mathbf{H} is the Jacobian matrix [40], [41]. The receiver state is updated iteratively as:

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{x}_k + \Delta \mathbf{x} \quad (9)$$

In conventional WLS, weights are chosen as $w_i = C/N_{0,i}/\sigma_{\rho,i}^2$ or similar heuristic functions. In our approach, we replace this with ML-predicted satellite scores:

$$w_i = f_{\text{ML}}(\text{features}_i) \quad (10)$$

where f_{ML} is the trained regression model. This ensures each weight reflects both signal quality and geometric contribution simultaneously.

D. Iterative WLS with Learned Satellite Weights

To operationalize the proposed weighting strategy within a standard iterative WLS solver, we integrate the trained machine-learning model as a per-satellite weighting function. At each iteration, the current receiver state is used to compute modeled pseudoranges and residuals, after which a feature vector is extracted for every visible satellite by combining signal-quality indicators with geometry-derived indicators. The ML model then predicts a satellite score that is directly mapped to the diagonal entries of the weighting matrix \mathbf{W} , enabling the estimator to adaptively down-weight unreliable measurements while preserving favorable geometric diversity. Algorithm 1 summarizes the complete ML-weighted WLS procedure.

Algorithm 1 ML-Weighted WLS for GNSS Positioning

Require: Pseudorange observations $\mathbf{y} = [\rho_1, \dots, \rho_n]^\top$; Satellite states; Initial receiver state $\mathbf{x}_0 = [x_r, y_r, z_r, b]^\top$; Trained ML model $f_{\text{ML}}(\cdot)$; Max iterations K ; Tolerance ε

Ensure: Estimated receiver position $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$

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1:  $\mathbf{x} \leftarrow \mathbf{x}_0$ 
2: for  $k = 0$  to  $K - 1$  do
3:   Compute modeled pseudoranges:  $\hat{\mathbf{y}} \leftarrow \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x})$ 
4:   Compute residual vector:  $\Delta \boldsymbol{\rho} \leftarrow \mathbf{y} - \hat{\mathbf{y}}$ 
5:   Compute Jacobian:  $\mathbf{H} \leftarrow \partial \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}) / \partial \mathbf{x}$ 
6:   for each satellite  $i = 1, \dots, n$  do
7:     Extract features:  $\mathbf{f}_i \leftarrow \text{Features}(i, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \text{sat\_data})$ 
8:     Predict weight:  $w_i \leftarrow f_{\text{ML}}(\mathbf{f}_i)$ 
9:   end for
10:  Form  $\mathbf{W} \leftarrow \text{diag}(w_1, \dots, w_n)$ 
11:   $\Delta \mathbf{x} \leftarrow (\mathbf{H}^\top \mathbf{W} \mathbf{H})^{-1} \mathbf{H}^\top \mathbf{W} \Delta \boldsymbol{\rho}$ 
12:   $\mathbf{x} \leftarrow \mathbf{x} + \Delta \mathbf{x}$ 
13:  if  $\|\Delta \mathbf{x}\|_2 < \varepsilon$  then
14:    break
15:  end if
16: end for
17: return  $\hat{\mathbf{x}} \leftarrow \mathbf{x}$ 

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IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND RESULTS

A. Dataset

The dataset used in this work is provided by the Google Smartphone Decimeter Challenge (GSDC), which offers high-quality GNSS measurements collected from commercial smartphones across urban and highway routes in San Francisco and Los Angeles [42], [43] (Fig. 4). The full dataset and its detailed description are available at the Kaggle Smartphone Decimeter Challenge page¹. Each trajectory includes raw GNSS logs (via the Android Location API) and centimeter-level ground-truth positions obtained from survey-grade equipment (NovAtel SPAN with ISA-100C IMU, Fig. 5). This dataset provides realistic smartphone-grade measurements (Fig. 6) under challenging conditions such as multipath and NLOS.

Each individual trajectory includes complete raw GNSS measurement logs obtained through the Android Location API, along with centimeter-level ground-truth positions acquired from survey-grade professional equipment. This carefully selected dataset provides realistic smartphone-grade measurements under challenging environmental conditions including severe multipath propagation, non-line-of-sight reception, and urban canyon effects. The diverse geographic coverage and challenging measurement conditions make this dataset particularly suitable for developing and validating robust positioning algorithms intended for real-world deployment in complex urban environments.

In total, we constructed a dataset of approximately 1.5 million samples. Each sample consists of the engineered features described above along with the target satellite score. Table II summarizes the dataset characteristics.

¹<https://www.kaggle.com/competitions/smartphone-decimeter-2023>

Fig. 3. Workflow of the proposed ML-WLS positioning approach.

Fig. 4. Road network covered by the dataset.

B. Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate the ML models, we split the dataset into 75% training and 25% testing. Performance was measured using the following metrics:

Mean Absolute Error (MAE):

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (11)$$

TABLE II
DATASET CHARACTERISTICS

Parameter	Description
Total Samples	1.5 Million
Environments	Urban Canyons, Highways
Smartphone Models	Xiaomi Mi-8, Google Pixel, Huawei, Samsung
GNSS Chipsets	Qualcomm, Broadcom, Samsung LSI, MediaTek
Signal Frequencies	L1 (1575.42 MHz), L5 (1176.45 MHz)
Constellations	GPS, GLONASS, Galileo, BeiDou

Root Mean Square Error (RMSE):

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (12)$$

Coefficient of Determination (R^2):

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (13)$$

where y_i is the true satellite score, \hat{y}_i the predicted score, \bar{y} is the mean of true scores, and N the number of samples.

Fig. 5. SPAN RTK vehicle frame.

Fig. 6. In-vehicle smartphone mounting setup for Google dataset collection.

TABLE III
MODEL EVALUATION METRICS

Model	MAE	RMSE	R^2
Linear Regression	260.565	840.457	0.001
SVR	1.834	6.302	-0.0002
Random Forest	4.798	58.083	-0.002
XGBoost	5.331	64.396	-1.084
DNN (MLP)	0.204	0.463	0.171

C. Model Evaluation

We compared Linear Regression (LR), Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Regression (SVR), XGBoost, and a Deep Neural Network (DNN/MLP). Table III reports the results.

The experimental results reveal insightful patterns. Classical machine learning approaches demonstrated inadequate performance with negative or near-zero R^2 values, indicating their fundamental inability to capture the complex non-linear relationships inherent in the satellite contribution scoring problem. In contrast, the DNN architecture exhibited substantially superior performance, achieving MAE = 0.204, RMSE = 0.463, and a positive R^2 value of 0.171.

Even if the R^2 value is still relatively small, it is a major improvement beyond baseline methods. The irregular nature of GNSS signal quality in complex environments and the existence of multiple unmodeled factors influencing satellite contribution are responsible for the relatively low R^2 . It is crucial to make clear that the anticipated satellite score is not a precise physical measurement but rather a synthetic

Fig. 7. Calibration plot of LR model on the validation set.

indicator. Following the complex WLS estimate procedure incorporating nonlinear geometry and associated measurement effects, this value represents each satellite's contribution to the positioning solution. Thus, in the WLS framework, a R^2 value of 0.171 can be considered adequate to generate adaptive weights. This assumption is further validated when integrating the predicted scores into actual WLS position calculation, as presented below.

To further assess prediction quality, we use calibration (reliability) plots that compare the mean predicted score to the mean ground-truth score within several prediction bins. Figs. 7–11 show that the DNN model curve is the only one aligned with the $y = x$ diagonal, indicating good calibration.

Fig. 8. Calibration plot of XGBoost model on the validation set.

Fig. 10. Calibration plot of RF model on the validation set.

Fig. 9. Calibration plot of SVR model on the validation set.

Following comprehensive hyperparameter optimization, including systematic tuning of network architecture, activation functions, and learning rate schedules, the DNN model was selected for integration into the positioning framework.

D. Experimental Configuration

For the positioning performance assessment phase, we employed the independent GSDC 2022–2023 dataset to ensure complete temporal separation from the training data, thereby

Fig. 11. Calibration plot of MLP model on the validation set.

providing an unbiased evaluation of generalization capability. The DNN-predicted satellite contribution scores were integrated into the WLS positioning algorithm as described previously.

The experimental evaluation encompassed comparative analysis between two weighting strategies:

- **Conventional WLS:** Employing traditional elevation and C/N_0 -based weighting schemes.
- **Proposed ML-WLS:** Utilizing weights derived from DNN-predicted satellite contribution scores.

Table IV presents comprehensive positioning error statistics

TABLE IV
POSITIONING ERROR STATISTICS AT VARIOUS PERCENTILES

Metric	Conv. WLS (m)	ML-WLS (m)	Improv.
25th Percentile	5.296	1.471	72.2%
50th (Median)	6.264	4.182	33.2%
75th Percentile	9.744	6.053	37.9%
95th Percentile	10.870	6.568	39.6%
Overall Mean	13.212	8.039	39.2%

TABLE V
DEVICE-SPECIFIC MEAN POSITIONING ERROR ANALYSIS

Device	Conv. (m)	ML-WLS (m)	Improv.
Samsung S21 Ultra	6.676	4.408	34.0%
Google Pixel 6 Pro	11.466	5.499	52.0%
Xiaomi Mi-8	7.395	4.021	45.6%
Complete Dataset	13.212	8.039	39.2%

TABLE VI
DEVICE-SPECIFIC STANDARD DEVIATION ANALYSIS

Device	Conv. STD (m)	ML-WLS (m)	Improv.
Samsung S21 Ultra	4.185	2.170	48.1%
Google Pixel 6 Pro	15.648	3.439	78.0%
Xiaomi Mi-8	4.720	2.330	50.6%
Complete Dataset	7.499	3.767	49.8%

comparing both approaches.

To validate generalizability across different hardware, we conducted device-specific analysis on representative smartphone models, as presented in Tables V and VI.

E. Analysis and Discussion of Results

The experimental results show solid proof for the suggested ML-WLS methodology's effectiveness. With a remarkable 72.2% decrease in error at the 25th percentile, the positioning accuracy improvements are more noticeable at the lower percentiles, suggesting significant mitigation of systematic errors under favorable conditions. The method's reliability in a variety of operational settings is validated by the constant improvements across all percentiles, ranging from 33.2% to 72.2%.

The device-specific analysis reveals interesting insights regarding hardware-dependent performance. The Google Pixel 6 Pro demonstrated the most substantial improvement (52.0% in mean error, 78.0% in standard deviation), suggesting that the proposed methodology is especially effective for devices experiencing higher baseline variability. The consistency improvements, as evidenced by standard deviation reductions ranging from 48.1% to 78.0%, indicate that the ML-WLS approach not only improves average accuracy but also significantly enhances positioning reliability.

These results establish that the integration of machine learning-based satellite contribution scoring with weighted least squares positioning yields substantial and consistent improvements across diverse devices and operational conditions.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a unified machine-learning-based satellite weighting framework for smartphone GNSS positioning. By jointly exploiting signal-quality indicators and

geometry-derived features, the method predicts per-satellite contribution scores and integrates them as adaptive weights in a Weighted Least Squares solver. In this way, the proposed approach overcomes the limitation of conventional methods that treat signal quality and satellite geometry separately, while remaining compatible with the classical WLS formulation.

Experimental results showed that the MLP model provided the most effective weighting approach. When included in the positioning pipeline, the suggested ML-WLS approach reduced the total mean positioning error from 13.212 m to 8.039 m, with similar gains across different percentiles and smartphone models. These findings show that enhancing low-cost GNSS location in degraded environments can be achieved through learning geometry-aware and signal-aware satellite weights. Future work will focus on incorporating inertial data and integrating historical information to further improve positioning performance.

REFERENCES

- [1] V. Hamza, B. Stopar, O. Sterle, and P. Pavlovčič-Prešeren, "Recent advances and applications of low-cost GNSS receivers: a review," *GPS Solutions*, vol. 29, no. 1, p. 56, Jan. 2025, doi: [10.1007/s10291-025-01815-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10291-025-01815-x).
- [2] T. G. R. Reid *et al.*, "Localization requirements for autonomous vehicles," *SAE Int. J. CAV*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 173–190, Sep. 2019, doi: [10.4271/12-02-03-0012](https://doi.org/10.4271/12-02-03-0012).
- [3] X. Guan, H. Ge, S. Nie, and Y. Ding, "Research on agricultural autonomous positioning and navigation system based on LIO-SAM and AprilTag fusion," *Agronomy*, vol. 15, no. 12, p. 2731, Nov. 2025, doi: [10.3390/agronomy15122731](https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy15122731).
- [4] S. A. Weaver, Z. Ucar, P. Bettinger, and K. Merry, "How a GNSS receiver is held may affect static horizontal position accuracy," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 10, no. 4, p. e0124696, Apr. 2015, doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0124696](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0124696).
- [5] Z. Wang, G. Yang, R. Huang, M. Li, and M. Zhu, "Multi-GNSS large areas PPP-RTK performance during ionosphere anomaly periods," Jan. 2025, doi: [10.20944/preprints202501.0855.v1](https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202501.0855.v1).
- [6] C. K. Seow and S. Y. Tan, "Non-line-of-sight localization in multipath environments," *IEEE Trans. Mobile Comput.*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 647–660, May 2008, doi: [10.1109/TMC.2007.70780](https://doi.org/10.1109/TMC.2007.70780).
- [7] B. Li, K. Zhao, and X. Shen, "Dilution of precision in positioning systems using both angle of arrival and time of arrival measurements," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 192506–192516, 2020, doi: [10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3033281](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3033281).
- [8] N. Zhu, J. Marais, D. Betaille, and M. Berbineau, "GNSS position integrity in urban environments: A review of literature," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 19, no. 9, pp. 2762–2778, Sep. 2018, doi: [10.1109/TITS.2017.2766768](https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2017.2766768).
- [9] P. D. Groves, *Principles of GNSS, Inertial, and Multisensor Integrated Navigation Systems*, 2nd ed. Boston, MA, USA: Artech House, 2013.
- [10] Y. Li, C. Cai, and Z. Xu, "A combined elevation angle and C/N0 weighting method for GNSS PPP on Xiaomi MI8 smartphones," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 7, p. 2804, Apr. 2022, doi: [10.3390/s22072804](https://doi.org/10.3390/s22072804).
- [11] D. Jing *et al.*, "A fast satellite selection algorithm based on hierarchical clustering and iterative subset optimization," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 17, no. 5, p. 853, Feb. 2025, doi: [10.3390/rs17050853](https://doi.org/10.3390/rs17050853).
- [12] A. Alluhaybi, P. Psimoulis, and R. Remenyte-PreScott, "An evaluation of optimization algorithms for the optimal selection of GNSS satellite subsets," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 16, no. 10, p. 1794, May 2024, doi: [10.3390/rs16101794](https://doi.org/10.3390/rs16101794).
- [13] Y. Quan, L. Lau, G. W. Roberts, X. Meng, and C. Zhang, "Convolutional neural network based multipath detection method for static and kinematic GPS high precision positioning," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 10, no. 12, p. 2052, Dec. 2018, doi: [10.3390/rs10122052](https://doi.org/10.3390/rs10122052).
- [14] S. Zheng *et al.*, "Improving the prediction of GNSS satellite visibility in urban canyons based on a graph transformer," *Navigation*, vol. 71, no. 4, p. navi.676, 2024, doi: [10.33012/navi.676](https://doi.org/10.33012/navi.676).
- [15] S. Kim and J. Seo, "Enhancing urban GNSS positioning reliability via conservative satellite selection using unanimous voting across multiple machine learning classifiers," 2025, arXiv, doi: [10.48550/ARXIV.2507.12706](https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2507.12706).

- [16] M. Li, G. Huang, L. Wang, and W. Xie, “Comprehensive classification assessment of GNSS observation data quality by fusing k-means and KNN algorithms,” *GPS Solutions*, vol. 28, no. 1, p. 21, Nov. 2023, doi: [10.1007/s10291-023-01557-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10291-023-01557-8).
- [17] L. Li, M. Elhajj, Y. Feng, and W. Y. Ochieng, “Machine learning based GNSS signal classification and weighting scheme design in the built environment: a comparative experiment,” *Satellite Navigation*, vol. 4, no. 1, p. 12, May 2023, doi: [10.1186/s43020-023-00101-w](https://doi.org/10.1186/s43020-023-00101-w).
- [18] T. Ozeki and N. Kubo, “GNSS NLOS signal classification based on machine learning and pseudorange residual check,” *Frontiers in Robotics and AI*, vol. 9, p. 868608, May 2022, doi: [10.3389/frobt.2022.868608](https://doi.org/10.3389/frobt.2022.868608).
- [19] Y. Lee and B. Park, “Nonlinear regression-based GNSS multipath modelling in deep urban area,” *Mathematics*, vol. 10, no. 3, p. 412, Jan. 2022, doi: [10.3390/math10030412](https://doi.org/10.3390/math10030412).
- [20] E. D. Kaplan and C. Hegarty, Eds., *Understanding GPS/GNSS: Principles and Applications*, 3rd ed. Boston, MA, USA: Artech House, 2017.
- [21] D. Prochniewicz, K. Wezka, and J. Kozuchowska, “Empirical stochastic model of multi-GNSS measurements,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 13, p. 4566, Jul. 2021, doi: [10.3390/s21134566](https://doi.org/10.3390/s21134566).
- [22] H.-I. Kim and K.-D. Park, “Satellite positioning accuracy improvement in urban canyons through a new weight model utilizing GPS signal strength variability,” *Sensors*, vol. 25, no. 15, p. 4678, Jul. 2025, doi: [10.3390/s25154678](https://doi.org/10.3390/s25154678).
- [23] Z. Lyu and Y. Gao, “An SVM based weight scheme for improving kinematic GNSS positioning accuracy with low-cost GNSS receiver in urban environments,” *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 24, p. 7265, Dec. 2020, doi: [10.3390/s20247265](https://doi.org/10.3390/s20247265).
- [24] N. Blanco-Delgado and F. D. Nunes, “Satellite selection based on WDOP concept and convex geometry,” in *Proc. 5th ESA Workshop NAVITEC*, Dec. 2010, pp. 1–8, doi: [10.1109/NAVITEC.2010.5708044](https://doi.org/10.1109/NAVITEC.2010.5708044).
- [25] H. A. Msaewe *et al.*, “Investigating multi-GNSS performance in the UK and China based on a zero-baseline measurement approach,” *Measurement*, vol. 102, pp. 186–199, May 2017, doi: [10.1016/j.measurement.2017.02.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2017.02.004).
- [26] M. Kihara and T. Okada, “A satellite selection method and accuracy for the Global Positioning System,” *Navigation*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 8–20, Mar. 1984, doi: [10.1002/j.2161-4296.1984.tb00856.x](https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2161-4296.1984.tb00856.x).
- [27] C.-W. Park and J. P. How, “Quasi-optimal satellite selection algorithm for real-time applications,” in *Proc. ION GPS*, Sep. 2001, pp. 3018–3028. [Online]. Available: <http://www.ion.org/publications/abstract.cfm?jp=p&articleID=1978>
- [28] M. Liu, M.-A. Fortin, and R. Landry, “A recursive quasi-optimal fast satellite selection method for GNSS receivers,” in *Proc. ION GNSS*, Sep. 2009, pp. 2061–2071. [Online]. Available: <http://www.ion.org/publications/abstract.cfm?jp=p&articleID=8618>
- [29] C.-S. Chen, Y.-J. Chiu, C.-T. Lee, and J.-M. Lin, “Calculation of weighted geometric dilution of precision,” *J. Applied Mathematics*, vol. 2013, pp. 1–10, 2013, doi: [10.1155/2013/953048](https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/953048).
- [30] Y. Zuo, Y. Yao, and M. Hu, “A new criterion construction and verification for GNSS satellite selection based on near-real-time accuracy,” *Sensors*, vol. 25, no. 23, p. 7218, Nov. 2025, doi: [10.3390/s25237218](https://doi.org/10.3390/s25237218).
- [31] P. Singh, J. Joshi, A. Dey, and N. Sharma, “GNSS satellite selection based on per-satellite parameters using deep learning,” *IETE J. Research*, vol. 70, no. 1, pp. 46–57, Jan. 2024, doi: [10.1080/03772063.2022.2121768](https://doi.org/10.1080/03772063.2022.2121768).
- [32] H.-F. Ng, G. Zhang, and L.-T. Hsu, “Robust GNSS shadow matching for smartphones in urban canyons,” *IEEE Sensors J.*, vol. 21, no. 16, pp. 18307–18317, Aug. 2021, doi: [10.1109/JSEN.2021.3083801](https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2021.3083801).
- [33] L.-T. Hsu, Y. Gu, and S. Kamijo, “NLOS correction/exclusion for GNSS measurement using RAIM and city building models,” *Sensors*, vol. 15, no. 7, pp. 17329–17349, Jul. 2015, doi: [10.3390/s150717329](https://doi.org/10.3390/s150717329).
- [34] D. Dutta *et al.*, “Studies on navigational satellite visibility and signal strength of different GNSS sensor,” in *Proc. IEEE EDKCON*, Nov. 2024, pp. 1–4, doi: [10.1109/EDKCON62339.2024.10870778](https://doi.org/10.1109/EDKCON62339.2024.10870778).
- [35] S. Kaiser, Y. Wei, and V. Renaudin, “Analysis of IMU and GNSS data provided by Xiaomi 8 smartphone,” in *Proc. IEEE IPIN*, Nov. 2021, pp. 1–8, doi: [10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662533](https://doi.org/10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662533).
- [36] Y. Teng and J. Wang, “A closed-form formula to calculate geometric dilution of precision (GDOP) for multi-GNSS constellations,” *GPS Solutions*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 331–339, Jul. 2016, doi: [10.1007/s10291-015-0440-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10291-015-0440-x).
- [37] T. K. Ho, “Random decision forests,” in *Proc. 3rd Int. Conf. Document Analysis and Recognition*, 1995, pp. 278–282, doi: [10.1109/ICDAR.1995.598994](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDAR.1995.598994).
- [38] V. N. Vapnik, “An overview of statistical learning theory,” *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw.*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 988–999, Sep. 1999, doi: [10.1109/72.788640](https://doi.org/10.1109/72.788640).
- [39] T. Chen and C. Guestrin, “XGBoost: A scalable tree boosting system,” in *Proc. 22nd ACM SIGKDD*, 2016, pp. 785–794, doi: [10.1145/2939672.2939785](https://doi.org/10.1145/2939672.2939785).
- [40] A. Pirsivavash, A. Broumandan, G. Lachapelle, and K. O’Keefe, “GNSS code multipath mitigation by cascading measurement monitoring techniques,” *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 6, p. 1967, Jun. 2018, doi: [10.3390/s18061967](https://doi.org/10.3390/s18061967).
- [41] P. Xu, J. Liu, and Y. Shi, “Almost unbiased weighted least squares location estimation,” *J. Geodesy*, vol. 97, no. 7, p. 68, Jul. 2023, doi: [10.1007/s00190-023-01742-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-023-01742-0).
- [42] G. Fu, M. Khider, and F. Van Diggelen, “Android raw GNSS measurement datasets for precise positioning,” in *Proc. ION GNSS+*, Oct. 2020, pp. 1925–1937, doi: [10.33012/2020.17628](https://doi.org/10.33012/2020.17628).
- [43] M. Fu, M. Khider, and F. van Diggelen, “Summary and legacy of the Smartphone Decimeter Challenge (SDC) 2022,” in *Proc. ION GNSS+*, Sep. 2022, pp. 2301–2320, doi: [10.33012/2022.18379](https://doi.org/10.33012/2022.18379).

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